

We can't keep doing all the things: Imagining and implementing sustainable evidence synthesis support

Jolene Miller, MLS, AHIP; Margaret A. Hoogland, MLS, AHIP; Jodi Jameson, MLIS; Wade Lee-Smith, MLS; Gerald Natal, MLIS, AHIP
The University of Toledo, Mulford Health Science Library, Toledo, OH

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Background

The Mulford Health Science Library began offering a systematic review (SR) support service in 2013. Like other health science libraries, however, the demand for SRs eventually outgrew capacity (Russell et al., 2022). Also, faculty and students had short timeline expectations and review questions were often not in line with SR methodology – a problem previously observed in the literature (Lipke & Price, 2025). While librarians at Mulford were eager to support faculty and students' SR projects, it became apparent that some projects might be better suited to other evidence synthesis (ES) types.

Objectives

The primary aim of this project was to develop a transparent and sustainable ES support service model that would:

- Optimize librarians' time investment
- Educate faculty, staff, and students about different ES types
- Direct researchers to the appropriate review type for their question, timeline, and other factors

Methods

In Spring 2025, librarians held planning discussions to create a refined Evidence Synthesis Support Service.

To identify key service components, strategies of other libraries' ES support models were reviewed including:

- Emory University, Woodruff Health Sciences Library
- Henry Ford Health, Sladen Library
- Mayo Clinic Libraries
- Touro University Nevada, Jay Sexter Library
- University of Manitoba, Mclean Health Sciences Library

Results

Mulford faculty librarians developed a final process structure for their revamped **Evidence Synthesis Support Service**, comprised of the following components:

- 1) Reviews and Evidence Syntheses LibGuide (<http://libguides.utoledo.edu/es>)** This new LibGuide serves as a first point of reference for faculty and students interested in conducting a SR or other ES type. It serves to inform researchers about the most appropriate ES options for their review question and timeline.
- 2) "Which Review is Right for You?" Decision Tree.** After reviewing the various ES types on the LibGuide, patrons are encouraged to complete a decision tree to further direct them to an appropriate ES type. This tree was created in Google Forms and is based on tools developed at the Maclean Health Sciences Library at the University of Manitoba & Sladen Library at Henry Ford Health.
- 3) Librarian Consultation and Guidance. If the decision tree recommends conducting a non-SR ES type:** patrons are advised to schedule a consultation with their liaison librarian for search strategy guidance or request a literature search.
- 4) Systematic Review Consultation Request Intake Form. If the decision tree recommends conducting a SR:** patrons are directed to the **Systematic Review LibGuide Page** (<https://libguides.utoledo.edu/es/sysrev>) linking them to a required intake form, based on PROSPERO's ES protocol registration records, prior to receiving librarian support.

Flowchart of the new evidence synthesis structure

Conclusions

Transition to a Consultation Model

Anticipated Benefits

- Increased transparency communicating the level of service librarians can provide
- Enables reasonable patron expectations
- Education about ES types is built into the new model which could result in higher quality, more publishable ESs
- New intake form for SRs forces patrons to conduct preliminary searching
- Librarians are better able to balance their workload to facilitate learning opportunities for SR teams
- Librarians' time is optimized so they can:
 - Direct patrons to appropriate ES types
 - Provide search strategy guidance for true SRs

Possible Limitations

- May increase number of SRs or other ESs conducted without librarian assistance

Ideas for Future Research

ES Support as Invisible Labor

- Previous literature has observed that SR support can be considered a type of "invisible labor" (Ross-White, 2021)
- How might this inform patrons' perceptions or expectations of librarian support for ESs?

Librarian Burnout and ES Support

- What is the connection between librarian burnout and ES support?
- Could an improved model help prevent burnout, especially for libraries without a dedicated informationist who devotes most of their workload to ES support?
- Demetres et al. (2020) found that respondents who used an SR support tool had significantly lower burnout scores; and respondents who reported spending >80% of their job duties on SR work had significantly lower burnout scores than those who spent <10% on SR work.

References

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